

Blockchain and Trustworthy Reputation for Federated Learning: Opportunities and Challenges

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Abstract—In the domain of Collaborative Artificial Intelligence, Federated Learning (FL) is a technique that enables multiple entities to collaboratively refine AI models while adhering to stringent data privacy standards, without the need for direct data sharing. This paper explores the integration of blockchain technology with FL to establish reliable trust mechanisms within this collaborative framework. We highlight and review current blockchain-enabled reputation mechanisms that evaluate the reliability and quality of contributions from participants, which are crucial for maintaining trust and operational integrity in distributed settings. Through our review, we address the concept and implementation challenges. Additionally, we discuss recent technological advances and explore the emerging opportunities that blockchain presents to address trust-related challenges in FL, emphasizing significant prospects for future research directions, such as decentralized identities, zero trust, and zero-knowledge proofs to enhance trust in these environments.

Index Terms—Blockchain, FL, AI, Trust, Reputation, Smart Contracts

I. INTRODUCTION

Collaborative Artificial Intelligence with Federated Learning (FL) exploits the power of distributed datasets to enhance artificial intelligence (AI) model training while upholding stringent data privacy standards. This methodology allows multiple entities to refine AI models collaboratively without exchanging underlying data, thus complying with strict privacy regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA). Integration with real-time data platforms like Kafka-ML facilitates dynamic, scalable training environments, rendering FL especially advantageous in sectors like healthcare and finance, where data sensitivity is critical [1]. FL can be implemented in various environments, including edge devices and multi-provider setups, among others. Specifically, when deployed on edge devices, FL must adapt to a range of environmental challenges that can impact data quality and model performance. These challenges include variations in battery power, sensor types, and processing capabilities. Additionally, factors like device mobility and limited battery life can lead to asynchronous model training. This asynchronous nature can result in delays and the use of outdated data, further complicating the training process. Secure communication is essential for knowledge sharing among devices, necessitating robust authentication and verification mechanisms to ensure

model integrity. Additionally, incentive mechanisms are vital for sustaining device engagement in FL collaborations.

Furthermore, FL inherently demands trust among participants, given the absence of direct data sharing, requiring mechanisms to ensure the integrity of the shared model and the fairness of the training process. Reputation models in FL contexts are crucial for establishing and maintaining trust by providing a transparent means to assess and validate the reliability and quality of contributions from each participant. These models leverage historical data and behavioral analysis to score each entity, influencing their impact in decision-making processes and ensuring that only trustworthy data influences the final model. This helps to mitigate risks associated with data poisoning and model tampering, thereby enhancing the overall security and effectiveness of FL systems [1]. Despite these challenges, FL remains a key strategy for collaborative intelligence in various industries in a privacy-conscious era. Blockchain technology has attracted significant attention for its potential to instill trust through features such as transparency and immutability, with smart contracts acting as key facilitators. The current research emphasis is on integrating blockchain, renowned for its decentralized nature and immutability, with FL [2], [3]. However, as blockchain technology evolves, new solutions are emerging, necessitating a deeper understanding and the identification of opportunities in collaborative AI to enhance trust [4] [5].

This article provides an initial overview of blockchain and FL, specifically emphasizing the role of trustworthy reputation mechanisms—a focus not extensively reviewed in existing literature. It outlines the current challenges and prerequisites necessary to enhance trust within collaborative AI frameworks and underscores the importance of further exploration into these areas. The article then identifies opportunities within reputation mechanisms for FL that remain under-explored but hold significant potential for advancing the field. Lastly, it discusses the challenges encountered in integrating these mechanisms, presenting this review to fill the critical gap in focused studies on the intersection of blockchain technology and reputation mechanisms in FL.

The structure of the article is as follow: Section II provides an overview of blockchain and collaborative AI in federated learning. In Section III, unexplored opportunities are highlighted along with an analysis of challenges. Finally, Section

V concludes the discussion.

II. BLOCKCHAIN-ENABLED REPUTATION MECHANISMS & FL: MOTIVATIONS AND REQUIREMENTS

A. Blockchain and Trustworthiness: Context and Overview

Blockchain technology underpins decentralized data storage by preventing single-entity control and ensuring data integrity. Validated transactions are immutably recorded on a blockchain, creating a traceable and secure chain that is resistant to modifications [6]. This unchangeable nature of the records is crucial as it establishes a foundation of trust among users. Blockchain’s consensus mechanisms, such as Proof of Work (PoW), Proof of Stake (PoS), and innovative approaches like Proof of Burn (PoB) and Proof of History (PoH), facilitate agreement among distributed processes, enhancing the reliability and security of the network [7]–[9].

Blockchains are differentiated by access permissions—permissionless for public access without oversight, and permissioned for restricted access with known user identities. This categorization influences the blockchain’s application in various industries, ranging from public blockchains that anyone can join to consortium blockchains that require complex cooperation among multiple organizations. The application of smart contracts, which execute transactions based on predefined conditions without intermediaries, further underscores blockchain’s capability to facilitate transparent and secure digital interactions [10].

The inherent transparency and immutability of blockchain technology are its most significant trust-enhancing features. All network participants can access and verify past and present entries, ensuring that data integrity is maintained and fraud risks are minimized. Such characteristics make blockchain an indispensable technology in sectors where secure, transparent transactions are critical, thereby bolstering overall confidence in digital ecosystems.

B. Federated Learning (FL): An Overview

FL represents a pivotal advancement in the field of AI, offering a privacy-centric approach that enhances collaboration without the need for sharing raw data. This method is particularly vital in environments where data privacy is paramount, as it allows participants to train a collective AI model while maintaining control over their data. By keeping sensitive information localized, FL ensures that data remains secure within its original location.

FL can be categorized into primarily two models based on how the data aggregation is managed: centralized and decentralized. In the centralized model, a central server aggregates model updates sent by participants, which can improve efficiency but may introduce privacy and single-point-of-failure concerns. In contrast, the decentralized model involves direct exchanges of model updates among participants without a central server, enhancing privacy and resilience against centralized threats but often requiring more sophisticated coordination and communication protocols. Under both models, FL operates on the principle where each participant (node) trains a model

locally on their data and then shares only model updates, not the data itself. The basic equation that describes the FL model update process is $w_{\text{global}} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K w_k$, where w_{global} is the updated global model, K is the total number of participating nodes, and w_k is the model update from the k -th node. This method ensures that the raw data remains with the data owner, thus enhancing data privacy and security.

The significance of collaborative AI with FL is underscored through practical applications such as next-generation internet technologies, like 6G, in which resource sharing and management across various organizations is expected to increase. For instance, multiple telecom operators might collaborate to enhance traffic management and public safety through a decentralized 6G network. Using FL, each operator trains AI models on local data collected via IoT devices and sensors, ensuring that sensitive data remains confidential. The operators share their model updates with a central server or directly with each other (depending on the FL model used), which then aggregates these updates into a comprehensive global model. This model is subsequently utilized to optimize real-time traffic routing and improve public safety measures without compromising data privacy. Such collaborative frameworks maximize the use of local data and AI capabilities across different operators, showcasing the transformative potential of collaborative AI through FL in adapting to dynamic urban conditions [11], [12].

C. Challenges

FL systems, whether centralized or decentralized, encounter challenges that primarily stem from trust-related issues. Both models face the need for constant authentication of participants, which is critical to ensuring the integrity of collaborative interactions and model updates. Maintaining and verifying the reputation scores of participants becomes essential in mitigating risks associated with the quality and reliability of contributions, helping to foster a trustworthy environment. Moreover, the verification of model submissions is a pivotal challenge. Both centralized and decentralized systems are susceptible to security threats such as model poisoning and inference attacks. The structure of decentralized systems, in particular, demands robust network management and secure data transactions to safeguard against these vulnerabilities, given their reliance on peer-to-peer interactions which can complicate coordination and communication.

Integrating blockchain technology offers significant benefits by enhancing security within these networks. Blockchain ensures that data exchanges are immutable and traceable, thereby securing transactions and mitigating the risk of malicious activities. Furthermore, trust penalization mechanisms embedded in blockchain can deter dishonest behaviors by diminishing the influence of nodes that submit poor-quality or malicious updates [13], [14]. Despite these advancements, the risk of “honest but curious” behavior persists, where participants might exploit updates to infer private data or manipulate the model for personal gain. This behavior can undermine trust, as participants must depend on each other to respect

the privacy and integrity of the data without direct oversight. Therefore, the continuous development and implementation of advanced security measures, such as cryptographic techniques are critical to safeguarding the integrity of FL environments. Both centralized and decentralized models inherently enhance user privacy by design, but the transmission of learning parameters remains vulnerable to security threats. Potential malicious attacks could severely compromise the system’s integrity, highlighting the need for more robust, decentralized approaches to effectively handle scalability and security challenges. Reputation mechanisms have been proposed to specifically address these issues by providing a means to validate and score the contributions of each participant based on their historical data and behavior. In the following section, we will delve deeper into how blockchain technology has been leveraged to enable trustworthy reputation mechanisms.

III. BLOCKCHAIN-ENABLED FL: REVIEW OF REPUTATION MECHANISMS

Over the years, FL has leveraged blockchain technology to address key challenges across various domains, including privacy preservation [25], [26], network security [27]–[30], medicine and healthcare for global models during pandemics [31]–[33], or the automotive sector [34]–[36]. Blockchain-enabled reputation mechanisms have emerged as critical tools in these efforts.

A. Review of Reputation Mechanisms

Reputation mechanisms are pivotal in FL systems [37], building trust among nodes and enhancing the trust and reliability of collaborative model training. These mechanisms evaluate participants based on their historical actions, such as the quality of their model updates and adherence to protocols, adjusting their influence on the aggregated model accordingly. High-performing participants exert greater impact, while those with lower scores might have their contributions down-weighted or excluded, thereby encouraging high-quality contributions and mitigating risks like model poisoning and data leakage.

Blockchain acts as a fundamental pillar for establishing trustworthiness in reputation mechanisms within both centralized and decentralized FL contexts. For centralized FL, blockchain’s immutable ledger transparently records and validates participants’ contributions, enhancing trust among collaborators. It securely stores each participant’s performance metrics, such as data quality and model improvements, ensuring accountability and incentivizing active engagement. In decentralized FL, blockchain supports the creation of reputation tokens or credits tied to each participant’s contributions, enhancing trust within the network. Smart contracts facilitate the automated distribution of rewards based on reputation scores, promoting fairness and transparency [38]. Furthermore, the implementation of blockchain enhances transparency and reliability within collaborative AI endeavors. By recording every update on the blockchain, all network members can independently verify and oversee training progress. Blockchain’s

decentralized nature reduces the need for centralized control during the aggregation phase, potentially lowering communication overheads and greater participation from mobile users [19].

Table II-C offers a comprehensive overview of research advancements focusing on integrating reputation mechanisms within FL environments to enhance security, reliability, and trust using blockchain technology. For instance, Yang et al. (2024) [15] employ blockchain, homomorphic encryption, and a reputation system to introduce privacy and security in the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), using a reputation system on a public blockchain to manage data integrity and node reliability. Similarly, Tang et al. (2024) [16] introduce a dual-reputation system employing a reverse auction mechanism for trustworthy client selection in IoT, aiming to mitigate the impact of malicious clients. Chen et al. (2024) [17], on the other hand, propose a framework that integrates blockchain to handle malicious activities and ensure fair reward distribution, utilizing smart contracts for transparency. Additional contributions include [18], who combine reputation metrics with secure shuffling for leader election in FL, alongside cryptographic techniques like fully homomorphic encryption to enhance decentralization. [19] and [21] further the discussion by implementing blockchain-based decentralized systems that use reputation-based incentives to improve model quality, with Wahrstatter et al. deploying these on Ethereum’s smart contract platform. Each of these studies not only advances the theoretical framework of FL but also addresses practical challenges like scalability, computational overhead, and the need for client authentication processes, highlighting the pivotal role of reputation systems in maintaining the integrity of decentralized learning networks.

Despite the advancements blockchain has brought to collaborative AI with FL, there remain gaps in each research, particularly in the areas of authentication, identity and access management, and verification. Many studies, such as those [15] and [16], while pioneering in integrating security features within FL systems, have not fully explored mechanisms for authentication and verification of clients. This absence is notable across various proposals, as most focus heavily on securing data and managing node reliability but overlook the critical aspect of securely authenticating clients and verifying model submissions. For example, [17] and [18] introduce sophisticated reputation and cryptographic systems to counteract malicious activities and ensure fairness, yet they do not address the urgent need for effective identity verification methods that can further secure the FL environments against impersonation and other identity-related attacks. This gap highlights a critical challenge in the field, underscoring the urgent need for future research to develop comprehensive solutions for identity management, along with verified authentication and model submission verification, to establish explicit trust.

Table I
REVIEW OF BLOCKCHAIN-ENABLED REPUTATION MECHANISMS FOR FL

Ref	Proposed Idea	Methodology	Blockchain Type	Gaps/Issues Not Tackled
[15]	Integrate blockchain, homomorphic encryption, and a reputation system into FL to enhance privacy and security in IIoT.	Utilizes homomorphic encryption for secure distributed training, and a reputation system on a blockchain to manage data integrity and node reliability.	Public	Potential scalability issues of blockchain, computational overhead of homomorphic encryption, absence of techniques for authentication of clients and model submission, verification to enhance trust.
[16]	Proposes a dual-reputation system using a reverse auction mechanism to enhance the reliability of FL in IoT by selecting trustworthy clients and reducing the impact of malicious clients.	Incorporates a dual-reputation mechanism to evaluate client reliability and a reverse auction method for client selection, coupled with adaptive dropout aggregation to minimize malicious impact.	Public	Does not specifically discuss the implications of implementing blockchain, absence of techniques for authentication of clients and model submission verification to enhance trust.
[17]	Design a trustworthy FL framework integrating blockchain to handle model and data poisoning by malicious clients and ensure fair reward distribution based on client contribution.	Proposes malicious model detection and a fair contribution evaluation method, using blockchain and smart contracts to ensure transparency and trust throughout the FL process.	Public	Absence of techniques for authentication of clients and model submission verification.
[18]	Combines reputation metrics with secure shuffling for leader election in federated learning, alongside cryptographic techniques like secret-sharing and fully homomorphic encryption to enhance security and decentralization.	Uses a reputation-based method for leader election, secure aggregation with homomorphic encryption, and verifiable secret sharing to prevent Byzantine behavior in decentralized settings.	Public	Does not address the potential need for cryptographic computations in resource-constrained environments, also absence of techniques for authentication of clients and model submission verification.
[19]	Proposes a blockchain-based decentralized FL system using reverse auctions and a reputation-based incentive mechanism to improve model quality.	Uses reverse auctions to encourage participation of reputable data owners, and a reputation system to assess and improve the quality of contributions based on model performance.	Public	Absence of techniques for authentication of clients and model submission verification to enhance trust.
[20]	Introduces optimization algorithms equipped with an incentive mechanism addressing excessive iterations and prolonged training duration in FL, enhancing model accuracy.	Integrates a reputation value calculation system and an Earth Mover's Distance (EMD) mechanism into FL to optimize data quality and reduce non-IID data impact, improving model training.	Public	Absence of techniques for authentication of clients and model submission verification to enhance trust.
[21]	Implements a scalable, open, and secure decentralized FL system on Ethereum to enable autonomous participant interaction without central oversight.	Deploys a collateral-backed reputation system to secure interactions and ensure honesty, using Ethereum's smart contract platform to handle FL processes among anonymous users.	Public	Absence of techniques for authentication of clients and model submission verification to enhance trust or how to mitigate the effects of Ethereum's scalability and transaction fee issues on system performance.
[22]	Enhance the security and reliability of FL by using a reputation evaluation system along with blockchain technology.	Utilizes a reputation system to assess the credibility of participating nodes, integrating blockchain to maintain a secure and tamper-proof record of reputations and transactions.	Private	Absence of techniques for authentication of clients and model submission verification to enhance trust or the computational overhead introduced by the reputation system.
[23]	Proposes a hierarchical blockchain framework with reputation management to improve the security of FL in mobile Internet of Vehicles environments.	Develops a hierarchical blockchain structure with a lightweight consensus algorithm (Proof of Quality - PoQ) and reputation management based on Bayesian theory and multiple subjective logic models.	Public	Does not discuss the specific challenges related to the real-time requirements of vehicular networks, nor does it address potential privacy concerns with the extensive data sharing and reputation scoring among participants.
[24]	Introduce blockchain-based reputation systems into (FL) to enhance trust and security in mobile edge computing systems.	Integration of blockchain technology for ensuring data immutability and traceability, combined with a reputation system to evaluate and incentivize participant behavior in FL environments.	Public	Absence of techniques for authentication of clients and model submission verification to enhance trust or the computational overhead introduced by the reputation system.

Figure 1. High-Level Architecture of a Blockchain-Enabled Federated Learning Framework with On-Chain and Off-Chain Processes

IV. BLOCKCHAIN-ENABLED REPUTATION MECHANISMS FOR FL: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

This section summarizes the discussion and provides an overview of lesson learnt by identifying opportunities to enhance blockchain-enabled reputation mechanism as well understanding challenges to implement these identified opportunities.

A. Opportunities

In response to above mentioned and identified gaps, particularly in authentication, identity, and access management, and verification this section outlines potential opportunities for future research. By integrating advanced blockchain concepts such as Decentralized Identifiers (DID), Zero Knowledge Proofs (ZKP), and Zero Trust architecture into reputation models, we can explore avenues to enhance trust and security in blockchain environments. These future directions aim to address the shortcomings in current studies by providing frameworks that can improve identity management and the integrity of model submissions, thereby strengthening the overall trustworthiness of collaborative FL systems.

Figure 1 presents a high-level view of a blockchain-enabled framework for trust in FL. It shows a bifurcation of operations into off-chain and on-chain processes. Off-chain, we have the FL Server, where an aggregator coordinates the learning process, and FL Clients, each with local data and a local model. The global model is improved through iterative updates from these clients. The identities imply a unique identification system for participants. On-chain, which refers to activities recorded on the blockchain, includes Smart Contracts, which govern interactions and transactions between the server and clients, ensuring trust, immutability, and verifiability. This structure is underpinned by a Decentralized Application (DApp), which operates atop the blockchain, providing a

user interface or automated backend functionality. Within this architecture, there is scope for incorporating advanced concepts like DID, ZKP, and ZT architecture at the DApp and Smart Contract level, offering pathways to further enhance trust, privacy, and security in collaborative environments. We proceed to elucidate these concepts and explore how blockchain can serve as a foundational technology to facilitate their implementation in such collaborative systems.

- Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) are a new type of identifier that support verifiable, self-sovereign digital identities, independent of centralized control. Unlike traditional identifiers managed by centralized entities, DIDs are entirely controlled by the identity owner and are independent of any central authority. When used with blockchain technology, DIDs ensure a secure, immutable, and tamper-proof system. Each DID links to a document that contains cryptographic materials and service endpoints for secure identity authentication. Owners can create and manage their DIDs independently, which are registered on a blockchain to ensure decentralized accessibility and tamper resistance [39].

In the context of collaborative AI, particularly within FL environments, DIDs substantially enhance security and trust. They allow for authentication of devices or nodes in an FL network, each having a unique DID. This setup enables verifiable credentials, ensuring that only authorized entities participate in model training. DIDs facilitate the decentralized management of access control, embedding rights and permissions directly into DID documents, which supports high levels of data privacy and integrity. In these environments, integrating DIDs with reputation mechanisms can enhance identity management. By authenticating and verifying the identities of participants through DIDs, the accuracy of reputation assessments can be improved, ensuring that contributions to the FL process are accurately attributed and that all interactions are reliably recorded and verified. This integration helps establish a trust framework crucial for verifiable transactions and secure data exchanges in collaborative AI, thereby fortifying security and simplifying administration in dynamic environments.

- The concept of Zero Trust security is essential in decentralized architectures like FL, where trust is never assumed and must be continually verified. This model fits well with the security demands of FL systems, with blockchain technology playing a crucial role by enforcing a Zero Trust approach. In this environment, neither FL servers nor clients automatically trust each other. Every interaction, whether an incoming connection or data from clients, is thoroughly verified. Blockchain enhances this setup by using smart contracts for explicit trust establishment and immutable record-keeping, which shifts the paradigm from implicit to explicit trust. In a Zero Trust FL system, blockchain not only verifies each transaction cryptographically but also maintains a continuous audit

trail, enhancing the trustworthiness of the system. This includes verifying the integrity and origin of data through cryptographic hashes and consensus mechanisms enhancing trust and resilience [40]. Additionally, integrating reputation mechanisms within this framework can improve authentication and access management. By continuously assessing the trustworthiness of each participant based on their interaction history and behavior recorded on the blockchain, a dynamic and responsive access control system can be established, further aligning with the principles of Zero Trust security. This approach ensures that only verified and trusted participants can access sensitive data and contribute to model updates, thereby enhancing the overall security of the FL process.

- Blockchain-enabled Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs) offer a cryptographic method that enhances trust and security in transactions and interactions by allowing a party (the prover) to confirm the truth of a statement to another party (the verifier) without revealing any information beyond the statement’s validity. For instance, Zero-Knowledge Machine Learning (ZKML)¹, is a blockchain platform that enhances transaction confidentiality and trust by utilizing advanced cryptographic protocols. This feature is especially valuable in environments where privacy and data integrity are paramount, such as in collaborative AI settings like Federated Learning. In FL, ZKPs enhance both privacy and trust by enabling proofs that data meets specific conditions—such as a dataset having entries that satisfy certain criteria—without exposing the data itself. This capability is crucial in sectors like healthcare or finance, where maintaining confidentiality is legally required. ZKPs ensure that data used in FL adheres to quality or compliance standards, transparency and trust without compromising the confidentiality of the data [41].

B. Challenges

Recent advancements in integrating blockchain technology with FL have brought significant attention to enhancing privacy and trust in decentralized systems across various sectors. However, there remain substantial areas requiring deeper exploration. Key technologies such as identity management and ZKPs have seen limited development. Despite some adoption of Zero Trust architectures, challenges related to scalability and integration persist. For instance, deploying zk-SNARKs² and managing the scalability of committee-based blockchains in dynamic environments pose ongoing difficulties [41], [42], [43]. Additionally, the computational demands associated with incorporating blockchain in systems like the Internet of Vehicles (IoV) and the broader challenges of applying these technologies in diverse settings are not sufficiently addressed [44], [45]. Issues such as the high transaction costs on Ethereum, slow transaction speeds, and the general need for enhanced blockchain performance are also critical areas that require further in-depth research and development [21], [46].

¹<https://zkml.gitbook.io/doc>

²<https://ethereum.org/en/zero-knowledge-proofs/>

Moreover, the cryptographic requirements of Zero Trust architectures and the effectiveness of blockchain consensus mechanisms are areas needing focused attention to improve security and efficiency [18]. Another significant challenge in blockchain systems is the integration of on-chain and off-chain processes. Leveraging off-chain computation and storage is crucial for managing heavy tasks and large datasets effectively. This integration is essential for enhancing system performance and scalability, highlighting the need for comprehensive research into optimizing these off-chain resources. Such developments could significantly improve reputation models within blockchain frameworks, making these systems more trustworthy and capable.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper has provided a comprehensive exploration of the integration of blockchain technology with Federated Learning (FL) to reinforce trust in collaborative AI applications. By leveraging blockchain-enabled reputation mechanisms, we have identified and addressed the key challenges and opportunities within distributed environments, underscoring the importance of such mechanisms in enhancing the reliability and quality of contributions. As the technological landscape evolves, the adoption of advanced blockchain features like decentralized identities, zero trust architectures, and zero-knowledge proofs offers promising pathways to augment trust and security in FL systems. Future research should focus on refining these integrations and overcoming the scalability and computational challenges to realize the full potential of blockchain-enhanced federated learning across diverse applications.

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